

DIABETES MELLITUS: PREVENTION AND TREATMENT

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One of the non-infectious (non-communicable) diseases that has been increasing dramatically among the population in recent years is diabetes mellitus. There are many misconceptions about this disease. Some of them are mentioned in the article.

"Diabetes is caused by fear", "Diabetes is a disease of the rich"...

There are two types of diabetes. Type 1 diabetes is an autoimmune disease. In addition, pancreatotropic (prone to live in the pancreas) viral infections (hepatitis, parotitis, rubella, measles, etc.) play an important role in its origin. In the origin of type 2 diabetes mellitus, inactivity, chronic consumption of products rich in easily digestible oleods, animal fat products in large and excessive amounts, and the formation of excess fat tissue accumulated in the body (mainly in the abdomen) are important.

In addition, chronic stress conditions, long-term insomnia, certain diseases, including hypertension, pancreatitis, obesity, thyrotoxicosis, Itsenko-Cushing syndrome, acromegaly and other diseases, as well as certain drugs (nicotinic acid, glucocorticoids, thyroid hormones) plays an important role in the development of diabetes.

Who is most likely to develop diabetes?

If a person leads a sedentary lifestyle, is obese, eats wrong (a lot and high calories), has high blood pressure, the probability of early onset of this disease increases.

Heredity also plays a big role in the origin of the disease.

How is blood sugar controlled?

The blood of all healthy people contains a certain amount of sugar (glucose) as the main source of energy. Sugar enters the blood in two ways:

1. With foods containing carbohydrates.
2. From glucose (glycogen) reserves in the liver.

As a source of energy, sugar enters muscle cells (for work), fat and liver tissue (for reserves). Sugar (glucose) enters the cells with the help of the insulin hormone produced by the pancreas.

After a person eats, the amount of sugar in the blood rises. But the pancreas immediately produces insulin and distributes it into the blood, and this insulin opens the gates of all cells for glucose. After glucose enters the cells, the amount of sugar in the deposit returns to normal. Between meals and during sleep, the blood sugar level is replenished from the reserve in the liver. This process is also controlled by insulin.

In type 2 diabetes, the pancreas produces insulin. But:

1. Insulin is not produced at the right time and in the right amount, and insulin production decreases over time.
2. Normally, 1 molecule of insulin is needed to open, say, 1 cell "gate" to glucose, but in type 2 diabetes several insulin molecules are needed. In other words, the body's resistance to insulin increases.

To make a diagnosis of diabetes, it is necessary to measure the amount of sugar in the blood in a laboratory.

What are the symptoms of diabetes?

Diabetes is manifested by constant weakness, frequent thirst, weight loss for no reason, feeling of hunger, frequent and large urination, wounds that do not heal for a long time, decreased sensation and pain in the legs, decreased vision.

When the blood sugar analysis is high for the first time, it is necessary to donate blood on a diet for reanalysis...

When a diet is prescribed, the amount of sugar in the blood is significantly reduced compared to the previous state, and it is not possible to assess the true state of carbohydrate metabolism. A patient suspected of having diabetes should eat normally until a definite diagnosis is made.

A patient with diabetes should be treated in an inpatient setting for 6 months...

The treatment of diabetes mellitus mainly consists of 4 components: diet, hypoglycemic agents, increased physical activity, and education about diabetes mellitus.

The patient must strictly follow this regimen every day. Complications of diabetes can be prevented or delayed only if the amount of sugar in the blood is always within the normal range during the day. Otherwise, it is impossible to prevent the complications of diabetes even if you are treated in the hospital for 10 days every month for 6 months. It is not indicated in any endocrinology or diabetology literature that 10 days of inpatient treatment is required every 6 months. Prevention of complications of diabetes is carried out by strict adherence to the regular regimen of treatment of the disease, as indicated above, and timely medical examination, general blood, general urine and biochemical

analyzes as indicated in the treatment standards, and taking measures based on their results.

TYPE 2 DIABETES AND ITS PREVENTION

Today, the number of people suffering from diabetes is increasing day by day. According to the World Health Organization, in 2013, 366 million people in the world were under control with diabetes, and by 2025, this number is estimated to reach 380 million on earth, but these estimates lag behind the actual incidence rate.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder. One of its symptoms is high blood sugar (hyperglycemia). This condition results from partial or complete cessation of insulin production by the pancreas. QD is divided into the first and second type. According to data, with QD 2 every 10 minutes a person gets sick, 1 patient dies, 200 children die every day, 7 million in a year. a person becomes ill with scurvy. 5-10% of the total incidence of QD is type 1 and 90-95%

Type 2 QD is correct. 80 percent of all patients are over 40 years old, and 5 percent of children under 15 years old.

Disease prevention. 1st type of QD belongs to the type of autoimmune diseases, and its prevention is considered one of the urgent tasks of medicine. Unfortunately, this problem has not yet been resolved did not find A healthy lifestyle is important to prevent type 2 diabetes. These include: being physically active, following a proper diet to do, to get rid of mental and physical stress, to maintain a normal body weight, not to consume tobacco and alcohol products as much as possible, to be aware of the first signs of the disease.

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